

Experimental analysis of sloshing-induced thermal mixing in horizontally oriented cylindrical tanks subjected to vertical acceleration

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Abstract

This work presents an experimental investigation of sloshing-induced pressure drop in a thermally stratified horizontal tank subjected to vertical harmonic acceleration. Using HFE-7000 as a cryogenic surrogate fluid, we simulate various sloshing intensities and fill levels under controlled thermal conditions. A simplified inverse method is applied to estimate time-resolved heat transfer coefficients and Nusselt number. The results identify two distinct phases: an initial pressure drop driven by vapor cooling, followed by a decay dominated by condensation.

1. Introduction

Understanding the thermodynamic behavior of cryogenic propellants under sloshing is essential for designing reliable liquid fuel tanks in aerospace and transport systems. This is particularly critical under dynamic conditions, where fuel motion and interface dynamics can destabilize pressure and affect heat transfer. Cryogenic fuels—especially liquid hydrogen (LH₂)—are attracting renewed interest due to their high specific energy, low emissions, and suitability for high-performance propulsion.²¹ Originally developed for space missions, they are now being explored for sustainable aviation and maritime transport. In aviation, horizontal cryogenic tanks pose unique challenges, as vertical accelerations during takeoff, turbulence, or maneuvers can disrupt the thermal stratification produced during long holding times, leading to increased heat and mass transfer and resulting in significant pressure fluctuations. These can compromise fuel feed stability and tank structural integrity.²⁰ A better understanding of interface dynamics, phase change, and transient thermal behavior is required to advance cryogenic propulsion into new domains.

Most experimental studies on non-isothermal sloshing systems have focused on upright cylindrical or spherical tanks, primarily in the context of space applications, aiming to identify the dominant mechanisms behind pressure drop. A consistent finding across these studies is the central role of thermal destratification and interfacial dynamics. For instance, experiments by Moran et al.²⁰ with a 1.7 m³ LH₂ tank showed that resonant sloshing frequencies trigger the strongest pressure collapse, accompanied by significant temperature redistribution. Similarly, Lacapère et al.¹³ combined LN₂ and LOx tests with numerical simulations to confirm that the breakdown of thermal stratification is the primary driver of pressure decay. Das and Hopfinger^{4,11} further demonstrated that large-amplitude interfacial waves intensify heat and mass transfer across the liquid-gas interface, reinforcing the connection between interface dynamics and pressure response. Building on this, Arndt et al.^{1,2} found that higher initial ullage pressures, which create steeper thermal gradients at the interface, lead to more pronounced and prolonged pressure drops. Their work also highlighted the role of non-condensable gases, which mitigate the pressure fluctuations by adding a constant pressure offset to the vapour pressure. Complementing these findings, Ludwig et al.¹⁴ observed that pressure decay tends to stall once a near-surface mixed layer forms, and identified a critical Reynolds number below which sloshing exerts negligible influence on pressure behavior.

Despite extensive work on upright tanks, the behavior of horizontally oriented tanks under vertical acceleration remains largely unexplored. This configuration, introduces distinct sloshing dynamics and thermal responses that may lead to different pressure drop mechanisms.⁸

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This work presents an experimental characterization of sloshing-induced pressure drop in an horizontal tank subject to vertical harmonic acceleration. The test section was placed on the 3-DoF SHAKESPEARE shaking table of the von Karman Institute to trigger sloshing. 3M Novec 7000 Engineered Fluid (HFE-7000) is a well-established cryogenic surrogate fluid, valued for its low surface tension, low viscosity, low saturation pressure, and low dynamic contact angle.^{6,7} Additionally, its low boiling point (35°C at 1 bara) greatly simplifies the design of experimental setups intended to replicate the self-pressurization caused by heat ingress in cryogenic storage during extended hold periods.

The testing apparatus included an active pressurization system and integrated heaters, enabling controlled and repeatable initialization of different levels of thermal stratification prior to sloshing events. It also featured a pre-treatment line for degassing, allowing the system to reach a single-species condition by removing dissolved gases. The combined use of temperature and pressure sensors was used to estimate the heat transfer coefficients using a simplified inverse method inspired by the approaches of Marques et al.^{16,17}

The experimental apparatus, testing procedure and data processing are described in Section 2 while results are reported in Section 3. Conclusions and outlooks are collected in Section 4.

2. Methodology

2.1 Test facility

The experimental campaign was carried out at the SHAKESPEARE facility (SHaking Apparatus for Kinetic Experiments of Sloshing Projects with EArthquake Reproduction) at the von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics. The shaking platform consists of a square table with a basis of 1.5 m × 1.5 m, capable of translational motion along three orthogonal axes through a system of independently actuated sliding modules, as depicted in Fig. 1-a. Each module is driven by a hydraulic piston actuator, with motion controlled by a central computer via a closed-loop feedback system incorporating high-precision position sensors. The apparatus allows for a maximum displacement of 45 mm along each axis and is capable of achieving peak accelerations of up to approximately 1.1 g. The system is designed to accommodate payloads of up to 500 kg. The central controller is capable of reproducing continuous acceleration signals. This work focuses on harmonic vertical oscillations that are relevant for aerodynamic applications.

Figure 1: (a) Shaking table facility SHAKESPEARE with schematic of the three motion axis modules.¹⁷ (b) Plexiglass sloshing cell.

Two identical replicas of the horizontal tank were manufactured and tested. These correspond to a 1:15 scale model of a full-scale LH2 aviation tank, with the main body measuring 312.25 mm in length and 134.5 mm in diameter. This geometry results in a first transverse natural frequency $\omega_{01} = 14 \text{ rad/s}$.⁹ The first apparatus, referred to as *isothermal*, consists of a 15 mm-thick cylinder of plexiglass (shown in Fig. 1-b), assembled with stainless steel side domes. The transparent wall provides optical access, enabling flow visualization and analysis of interface dynamics. In the second apparatus, referred to as *non-isothermal*, the cylinder is made of 3.5 mm-thick stainless steel to allow for setting up the non-isothermal conditions (Fig. 2-right) with large temperature variations. The main body is assembled with stainless steel side domes, while all internal materials (e.g., seals) are made of chemically compatible materials, allowing operation with HFE-7000 as a working fluid. The tank is mounted on aluminum feet, which are securely bolted to an aluminum base plate. This plate serves as a mechanical interface for integrating a tri-axial load cell, enabling force measurements. This tank was connected to a pressurizing tank (Fig. 2-right) via a flexible line to set up the non-isothermal conditions before sloshing through an active-pressurization procedure.

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The underlying assumption behind the investigation with two tanks is that the sloshing dynamics have a significant impact on the thermodynamics of the ullage gas; however, thermal effects do not appreciably influence the sloshing regime. This allows us to characterize the sloshing dynamics on the first and study its thermal effects on the second. This assumption was based on preliminary numerical investigations and experimentally confirmed in.¹⁸

As further detailed below, the non-isothermal conditions were achieved by injecting warmer vapor prior to sloshing. To this end, the non-isothermal setup is equipped with valves to regulate mass flow or isolate the tanks during different experimental phases, and it is equipped with connectors for temperature and differential pressure sensors to monitor the thermal conditions. The pressurizing line is fitted with a flexible heater (Vulcanic 26175.12) and is thermally insulated to minimize condensation of superheated vapor along its pathway. This apparatus is additionally equipped with a 2 bara relief valve (Swagelok SS-RL4S8-EP) and polyamide flexible heaters (Omega KHLVA-104/10) with a power output of 10 W/inch², ensuring precise thermal control during experiments. Furthermore, it includes a vapor diffuser to minimize interface disturbance during the injection.

Figure 2: Non-isothermal sloshing cell: drawing with dimensions in millimeters, internal volume highlighted in green, and thermocouple positions marked with red circles (left); 3D isometric view (right) showing the relief valve SV2 (1), vapor diffuser (2), connector for thermocouples (3), pressure transducer (4), differential pressure sensors (5), and liquid inlet.

Figure 3: Pressuring tank with main components (left): vacuum KF connector V2 (1), pressure transducer P001 (2), safety valve SV1 (3), pressuring line connector V3 (4), heating belts (5), wall type K thermocouple T13 (6), fluid mixer (7), filling liquid line connector V6 (8), differential pressure sensor L001 (9), immersed type T thermocouple T1 (10). Photo of the non-isothermal setup (right).

The pressuring tank acts as a storage tank for the sloshing cell, providing saturated single-species liquid at ambient temperature for the initial cell filling and superheated vapor to pressurize the sloshing cell. This tank (see

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Fig.3-left) is equipped with a stainless steel tri-blade propeller with a 0-150 rpm controller, driven by a motor installed on the top. This mixer prevent thermal stratification and allows to ease the single-species procedure. Two heating belts (Vulcanic 7507.14, 1 kW each) are integrated with a PID control system to regulate the fluid temperature.

2.2 Measuring apparatus

Time-resolved imaging during the isothermal measurements was conducted using a transparent test section, high-speed cameras, and a background-light visualization technique. This setup enables detailed observation of sloshing dynamics and liquid motion. The camera used, a JAI SP-CXP4-F, is equipped with a monochrome APS-C CMOS sensor with a resolution of 12 megapixels (4096×3072 pixels) and a pixel pitch of $5.4 \mu\text{m}$. The system is fitted with Nikon AF 35mm f/2D lenses.

In the non-isothermal experiments, the measuring apparatus consists of five internal type K thermocouples mounted along a vertical probe positioned inside the sloshing cell. The vertical placement of each thermocouple is illustrated in Fig.2. For the fill levels employed in the present experiments (FL = 46-50%), only the lowest thermocouple is submerged in the liquid phase. At the same time, the remaining sensors are exposed to the vapor phase in the ullage region. Vapor pressure is monitored using an absolute pressure transducer (Swagelok PTI-S-AC3-32AQ-B), operating over a measurement range of 0 to 4bara, with a specified accuracy of $\pm 0.25\%$ full scale (FS). Additionally, a differential pressure transducer (PMI CS14-AA00001PD4A-3) connected to the top and bottom extremities of the cell allowed us to measure hydrostatic pressure for fill level determination. These sensors operate over a range of 0 to 68 mbara and offer an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$ of the Best Fit Straight Line (BFSL).

2.3 Experimental Procedure

The first set of experiments is conducted under isothermal conditions to provide a visual reference of the interface behavior and flow dynamics of HFE-7000, subjected to the same excitation profiles that was later applied to the non-isothermal test section.

In the isothermal experimental campaign, both the test section and the high-speed camera system were mounted on the sloshing table to ensure synchronized motion during excitation. The test section was filled with liquid HFE-7000 to reach the fill levels specified in Table 1. Careful filling procedures were followed to ensure repeatability and accuracy in the initial conditions across different runs. Once the desired fill level was achieved, the system was subjected to controlled excitations, and the flow dynamics were captured using time-resolved imaging for subsequent qualitative analysis of the interface behavior.

To ensure a single-species system and well-defined, repeatable thermodynamic conditions, a controlled initialization procedure was implemented before sloshing excitation.

Single-Species Procedure. Establishing a single-species system maximizes the sloshing-induced pressure drop by isolating condensation effects, enabling controlled and repeatable reproduction of the largest possible pressure drop. Nevertheless, achieving single species conditions with HFE-7000, presents a major challenge due to its high gas solubility (approximately 31% by volume under atmospheric conditions). Among the degassing techniques commonly employed to remove dissolved gasses,¹⁵ the most widely adopted are the Freeze-Pump-Thaw and Pressure-Reduction methods. In the present study, the Pressure-Reduction technique is implemented. Details on the procedure and results were presented by Monteiro et al.¹⁸

Test Procedure. The experimental protocol for conducting a sloshing test is organized into four phases. The procedure begins with filling the pressurizing tank to approximately 80% of its total volume. The single-species preparation process immediately follows this. Once a single-species condition is established within the pressurizing tank, the next phase involves characterizing the dynamic response of the sloshing cell to imposed acceleration.

In the third phase, saturated liquid HFE at ambient temperature is transferred from the pressuring tank to the vacuumed sloshing cell by gravity; see Fig. 2. The filling is performed until the desired fill level is reached, with a margin accounting for a certain degree of condensation during the pressurization.

In the fourth phase, the heating system is initiated in the pressurizing tank and sloshing cell. The heater belts around the pressurizing tank are activated to raise the vapor temperature and build up its pressure. Simultaneously, preheating is applied to the pressurization line to mitigate condensation and maximize pressure build-up during active pressurization. The heaters located on top of the sloshing cell are activated to develop a thermal stratification of the walls. Additionally, the piping of the differential pressure measurement equipment is warmed to evaporate residual liquid and prevent false fill-level readings. PID controllers individually regulate all heaters to ensure stable temperatures. Once sufficient pressure level is reached in the pressuring tank and stable thermal stratification of the walls is achieved in the sloshing cell, the procedure continues as depicted in Fig. 4. Superheated vapor is injected into the sloshing cell until a target pressure of 170 kPa is reached. A relaxation time is then respected to allow the test section to stabilize to a

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pressure of approximately 105 kPa and develop a well-defined thermal stratification. This relaxation phase is essential to ensure repeatable experimental conditions and reproduce realistic initial thermodynamic conditions obtained under self-pressurization driven by low external heat fluxes. As illustrated in Fig.8, the ullage initially approaches a uniform temperature during vapor injection. Gradually, stratification forms: temperatures near the tank walls remain high due to external heating, while those near the liquid-vapor interface drop due to condensation.

Figure 4: Graphical overview of the experimental procedure. During the first phase, the system is pressurized with warmer vapor. In the second phase it is allowed to "relax" while the third phase is the sloshing phase. Sloshing is carried out for 120 seconds in all tests.

Figure 5: Temperature evolution at the 5 measurement points within the sloshing cell during active pressurization and relaxation. The vertical lines denote the start and end of the warm vapor injection, $t = 0$ marks the initiation of the sloshing signal. The shadow area corresponds to the uncertainty of the measurement.

Experimental matrix. In this study, we impose a vertical harmonic displacement $a_e \cos(\omega_e t)$ with acceleration ranging from 0.17 to 0.49g for 120 seconds. Because a vertically excited tank will respond at half the excitation frequency,¹² we drive it here at twice the first transverse natural frequency of the half-filled tank to trigger instabilities. We have $\omega_e = 2\omega_{01} = 28$ rad/s. The detailed test matrix, which outlines the specific combinations of excitation parameters (i.e. acceleration, amplitude, and fill-level) used in this study, is provided in Table 1.

2.4 Thermodynamic Modeling of the sloshing induced pressure drop

After pressurization and relaxation, the liquid is sub-cooled and the vapor superheated relative to the interface. Sloshing then enhances thermal mixing, gradually warming the liquid and cooling the vapor. Owing to the liquid's higher thermal inertia, the interface cools, lowering the saturation pressure and causing an overall tank pressure drop.

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Test ID	$a_e \omega_e^2 / g$	a_e / R	h/D	Strong thermal mixing	Pressure drop
RUN-1.2	0.17	0.048	0.46	NO	NO
RUN-1.4	0.35	0.095	0.46	NO	NO
RUN-1.5	0.49	0.133	0.46	YES	YES
RUN-1.4.1	0.35	0.095	0.49	YES	YES
RUN-1.6	0.49	0.133	0.50	YES	YES

Table 1: Experimental matrix.

Experimental data from previous studies suggest that the pressure drop induced by sloshing can be well approximated by an exponential decay. Figure 6 presents the normalized pressure evolution obtained from various sources,^{1,13,14} with the time axis normalized by the characteristic time scale t^* , defined as the time required for the pressure to reach a steady-state value. For comparison, several exponential decay curves are also shown.

Figure 6: Normalized pressure drop over time from various experiments reported in the literature. Time is non-dimensionalized by the characteristic time required to reach a stable pressure value, while pressure is normalized such that it decreases from 1 to 0. The experimental data are compared with a reference exponential decay curve defined by $p(t) = e^{-t/\tau}$, with variable τ .

Assuming an exponential pressure decay of the kind $p(t) = p_\infty + (p_0 - p_\infty) e^{-t/\tau_p}$, with model parameters fitted to experimental data, provides a straightforward method to estimate the respective contributions of cooling and condensation to the overall pressure drop. This approach also enables the retrieval of the system's heat transfer coefficient under reasonable thermodynamic assumptions. Both aspects are addressed in the following sections: a "global" analysis of the thermodynamic state before and after sloshing is presented in Section 2.4.1, followed by an "instantaneous" analysis in Section 2.4.2.

2.4.1 Global variable approach

Considering t^* the time where the pressure starts to decay, the ullage is thermally stratified and superheated, the average temperature in the vapor is $T_v(t^*) > T_{sat}(t^*)$. Two main contributions to the pressure drop can be identified. The first relate to the pressure drop associated to the cooling from $T_v(t^*)$ to the saturation (interface) temperature evaluated at the time t_{ph} where $T_{vap} = T_{sat}$. Neglecting the volume variation and modeling the vapor as an ideal gas, the pressure drop associated to this contribution reads

$$\Delta p^{sup} = p(t^*) \frac{T_v(t^*) - T_{sat}(t_{ph})}{T_v(t^*)}. \quad (1)$$

The second contribution is linked to cooling of the interface, which reduces the saturation temperature and hence the saturation pressure. Neglecting variations of the latent heat of condensation \mathcal{L} within the range of thermodynamic states explored and assuming phase equilibrium, this contribution can be estimated using Clausius-Clapeyron equation

$$p(t_f) = (p(t^*) - \Delta p^{sup}) \exp\left(-\frac{\mathcal{L}}{\mathcal{R}} \left(\frac{1}{T_{sat}(t_f)} - \frac{1}{T_{sat}(t^*)}\right)\right), \quad (2)$$

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where \mathcal{R} is the specific gas constant and $T_{sat}(t^*)$ is the saturation temperature at the beginning of the pressure drop. Figure 7 illustrate the temperature evolution during the sloshing test RUN.15 (refer to Table 1) for several thermocouples, located at different heights within the cylinder. This condition produce a complete destratification and hence the largest possible pressure drop.

After approximately $t \approx 25$ seconds, all temperatures collapse into a single value, which closely match the saturation temperature obtained from the pressure measurements at the post-sloshing conditions. The liquid approaches the same value (see bottom thermocouple), albeit with some delay. The final pressure $p(t_f)$ is compared in section 3.3 to the experimental data to check the validity of the formulation used in this approach.

Figure 7: Temperature evolution for RUN-1.5. Solid lines refers to temperature of the gas, dashed line is the thermocouple in the bulk liquid, the saturation temperature is evaluated by the pressure measurement. The dotted line in the plot corresponds at $t = t^*$, time when the pressure drop starts. Note that the sloshing starts at $t = 0$, but the mixing occurs much after.

2.4.2 Time dependent heat transfer computation approach

The time-dependent analysis is based on the energy balance for the system under the assumption of exponentially decaying pressure evolution. In this analysis, we disregard the initial transient of the experiment (cf. Figure 7), that is the time interval within which the sloshing is not yet strong enough to produce mixing. Video recordings from identical experiments on the transparent tank shows that during this time the sloshing amplitude is still minor. Interestingly, the mixing and the associated pressure drop occur suddenly once the sloshing amplitude has reached a critical amplitude.

Focusing on the pressure reduction phase, pressure variation can be linked to the condensation rate dm_v/dt , temperature variation dT_v/dt and volume variation dV_v/dt by differentiating the equation of state for the vapor in time:

$$\frac{dp_v}{dt} = \frac{1}{V_v} \left(\frac{\partial p_v}{\partial \rho} \right)_T \frac{dm_v}{dt} + \left(\frac{\partial p_v}{\partial T} \right)_\rho \frac{dT_v}{dt} - \frac{m_v}{V_v^2} \left(\frac{\partial p_v}{\partial \rho} \right)_T \frac{dV_v}{dt}. \quad (3)$$

In this analysis, the vapour temperature $T_v(t)$ is interpreted as the average vapour temperature and was computed by averaging the signals from all sensors in the ullage volume. In what follows, we neglect the volume variation, since the reduction of ullage volume due to the condensation is negligible. The energy balance for the ullage vapor considering exchanges of heat and mass can be written as

$$\frac{dU}{dt} = -hA(T_v - T_l) + h_{sat} \frac{dm_v}{dt}, \quad (4)$$

where $U(t) = m_v u(T_v(t))$ is the total internal energy in the vapor, h is the heat transfer coefficient, A is the interface area (at rest), $T_v(t)$ and $T_l(t)$ are the time varying temperature for the vapor and the liquid phase, taken respectively as the average temperature from the thermocouples on each side and $h_{sat}(T_s(t))$ is the specific enthalpy of the vapor in saturation conditions. We emphasize that (4) adopts a global approach, defining the heat transfer coefficient relative to the system's lowest temperature. The energy balance accounts for both vapor-liquid and vapor-solid exchanges, without distinguishing their individual contributions.

Differentiating on the left-hand side gives:

$$\frac{dU}{dt} = m_v \frac{du}{dT_v} \frac{dT_v}{dt} + \frac{dm_v}{dt} u_{sat}(T_v) = -h(t)A(T_v(t) - T_l(t)) + h_{sat}(T_v) \frac{dm_v}{dt}. \quad (5)$$

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The terms related to the thermophysical properties of the fluid (du/dT_v , $u_{sat}(T_v)$, $h_{sat}(T_v)$) can be computed from dedicated libraries such as Coolprop.³ Combining equations (5) and (3) and using the measurement data on $p_v(t)$ and $T_v(t)$ allows for retrieving the unknown terms $h(t)$ and dm_v/dt . Using the exponential fitting (see Figure 10), one can circumvent limitations associated with the acquired data, although more advanced filtering and estimators could be implemented as in.¹⁷

By using the specific enthalpy definition the heat transfer coefficient is evaluated by using equation (6) used in section 3.4 the computed heat transfer coefficient will appear in the form of the Nusselt non-dimensional number.

$$h(t) = - \left(m_v \frac{du}{dT_v} \frac{dT_v}{dt} - \frac{dm_v}{dt} \frac{p_v(t)}{\rho_v} \right) \left(\frac{1}{A(T_v(t) - T_l(t))} \right) \quad (6)$$

2.5 Sensitivity analysis of thermodynamic sloshing behavior

A sensitivity analysis of the thermodynamic evolution under sloshing was also carried out using standard methods from Design of Experiments (DoE).¹⁹

The underlying idea is to fit a polynomial model between some input and output variables (herein referred to as factors) and use this model to evaluate the sensitivity. The input factors considered in this work are (1) the temperatures of the liquid at the tank bottom (T_l), (2) the temperature of the vapour on the top (T_v), (3) the amplitude of the vertical acceleration g and (4) the tank fill level in percentage (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Factors and responses considered for the sensitivity analysis.

The output factors (responses) are the temperatures T_l and T_v and the tank pressure p_v at the end of the sloshing phase. In this work, we focus on the tank pressure response only. As a general model, a cubic polynomial was implemented as a set of independent univariate mappings, each describing one output component separately, rather than as a single multivariate model capturing their joint behavior. The general cubic model for four input factor reads:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^4 \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^4 \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i < j} \beta_{ij} X_i X_j + \sum_{i=1}^4 \beta_{iii} X_i^3 + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ j \neq i}}^4 \beta_{iij} X_i^2 X_j + \sum_{i < j < l} \beta_{ijkl} X_i X_j X_l + \epsilon \quad (7)$$

where X_i , X_j are the input factors, Y the generic response, the 35 coefficients β_0 , β_i , β_{ii} , β_{ij} are the regression coefficients to be identified and ϵ the regression residual.

The model was trained on a larger database of 36 sloshing tests, comprising 5 acceleration amplitudes for the forcing, 34 fill levels and various initial liquid and vapor temperatures.

The coefficients β are identified using standard least square¹⁰ and the statistical significance of the resulting model was analyzed using Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA⁵). The ANOVA table partitions the total variability in the observed response data into components attributable to the model and to random error, allowing a comparison of their relative magnitudes. This comparison is quantified by the F value, defined as the ratio of the mean square due to the model to the mean square due to error. The associated p-value indicates how likely it is to observe such a ratio under the given data; smaller values suggest that the model explains a meaningful portion of the variability.

3. Results

3.1 Interface visualization

The images obtained from the isothermal campaign are presented in Fig. 9. The left column (panels (a) to (e)) corresponds to Run-1.2, a case not affected by significant pressure drop or thermal mixing. In contrast, the right column (panels (f) to (j)) corresponds to Run-1.6, where both pressure drop and thermal mixing are clearly observed, as shown in Sec.3.2. The instantaneous images shown in the first three rows reveal that, in Run-1.2, the liquid-vapor interface undergoes low-amplitude wave motion. Conversely, Run-1.6 displays pronounced interface deformation, characterized by splashing, wave breaking, and the formation of vapor bubbles within the liquid phase due to interfacial fragmentation. The interface structure observed in Run-1.6 resembles the (2,0) sloshing mode,⁹ which is symmetric in both the longitudinal and transverse directions.

Fig. 9 also includes time-averaged images for both cases (panel (d) and (i)). These averages show little difference between the two runs, indicating that over the acquisition period, the interface remained approximately centered around its initial position. However, a clear contrast emerges when examining the standard deviation of light intensity at each pixel (panel (e) and (j)). In Run-1.2, the fluctuations remain small and localized, consistent with weak sloshing activity. In Run-1.6, by contrast, the amplitude of interface motion is significantly higher, with pronounced vertical excursions extending from the liquid bulk into the ullage region, indicating strong sloshing.

3.2 Thermodynamic response

This section discusses the experiments in Table 1, which explore the effects of varying acceleration and fill level on temperature and pressure evolution. At $t = 0$, a harmonic acceleration at 3.7 Hz is applied, with amplitude adjusted to vary the acceleration level. Initially, temperature and pressure remain nearly constant, as shown in Figures 10 and 11. When liquid motion intensifies, thermal mixing increases, driving the fluid toward saturation by equalizing its temperature. This thermal destratification also cools the interface, leading to a pressure drop.

Both acceleration and fill level play a key role: at constant fill, a pressure drop occurs above a certain acceleration threshold; at constant acceleration, it appears above a critical fill level. This trend aligns with the isothermal case, where resonance in liquid motion arises once the amplitude and frequency of vertical excitation exceed a threshold for a given fill level. Following the pressure drop, the temperature of the saturated system begins to rise, causing a corresponding increase in pressure. This results from the vapor heating upon contact with the warmed tank walls.

The temperature evolution shown in Fig. 11 clearly reveals two distinct behaviors. In Run-1.2 and Run-1.4, unlike the other three cases, no significant thermal mixing is observed; vapor temperature shows a slight decrease while the liquid temperature remains nearly constant. In these runs, the excitation is not strong enough to trigger resonance, so thermal mixing remains weak throughout, and the only noticeable effect is a gradual cooling of the vapor due to the initial thermal gradient, with the interface temperature staying steady. In cases with a pressure drop, the data follow an exponential decay, as shown in Fig. 10 and consistent with literature (Fig. 6). The decay begins after a delay t^* , associated with the onset of resonance, which varies with initial conditions and acceleration and cannot be predicted in advance, though it falls within a characteristic time window. In RUN-1.4.1, RUN-1.5, and RUN-1.6, strong thermal mixing rapidly drives the system toward uniform saturation, with vapor cooling occurring faster than liquid heating, as illustrated in Fig. 7.

3.3 Global variable computations

The global approach decomposes the total pressure drop into two components: one from superheated vapor cooling and the other from phase change at the interface. As shown in Table 2, the phase change contribution (Δp^{ph}) clearly dominates over vapor cooling (Δp^{sup}), accounting for the majority of the observed pressure drop. The total computed drop slightly underestimates the experimental values, with errors around 5%.

Test ID	Δp^{sup} [kPa]	Δp^{ph} [kPa]	$\Delta p^{Tot model}$ [kPa]	Δp^{exp} [kPa]	Error [%] [kPa]
RUN-1.4.1	0.28	16.72	17.0	17.93	-5.19
RUN-1.5	0.49	15.24	15.73	16.41	-4.10
RUN-1.6	0.65	22.31	22.96	24.05	-4.53

Table 2: Pressure drop using the global approach and comparison with the experimental data.

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Figure 9: Left column: images from Run-1.2. Right column: corresponding imaging data from Run-1.6, where both pressure drop and thermal mixing are present. Panels (a) to (c) and (f) to (h) show randomly selected frame samples from each run, respectively. The fourth rows ((d) and (i)) display the time-averaged image, while the fifth ((e) and (j)) rows show the standard deviation of pixel intensity over time with grayscale colormap inverted.

3.4 Time dependent Nusselt

To assess heat transfer in the vapor phase, the Nusselt number is computed from the heat transfer coefficient h (as described in Section 2.4.2), using the tank radius r and the vapor thermal conductivity κ_v , that is $Nu = hr/\kappa_v$

Figure 12 shows the time evolution of the Nusselt number for the three cases in which a pressure drop is observed. As expected, the cases with the highest Nusselt numbers also exhibit the largest pressure drops, since the sloshing enhanced heat transfer in the vapor phase—primarily driving condensation—is the dominant mechanism responsible for the observed pressure reduction. The values of Nusselt obtained are significantly larger than what observed for lateral sloshing in upright cylindrical tanks of comparable size^{14,17} and, according the analysis in Ludwig et al¹⁴ even comparable to the one produced in the experiments by Moran et al²⁰ with a significantly larger tank.

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Figure 10: Tank pressure evolution for the different test considered. The dashed line shows the fit with an exponentially decaying law.

Figure 11: Tank temperature evolution in time for the different cases. The solid line corresponds to the thermocouple T8 on the top gas volume, the dashed line corresponds to the liquid temperature refers to thermocouple T12.

Figure 12: Nusselt number computation. All the test on the plot start from the moment where the pressure starts to decay at t^* , different for each case.

3.5 Sensitivity Analysis

The results of the regression-based sensitivity analysis and the corresponding ANOVA are presented in Table 3, while Table 4 summarizes the model performance metrics. Although the overall R^2 values indicate that the cubic models have limited predictive accuracy, they still provide valuable insight into the sensitivity of the pressure response to the four

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input factors considered: vapor temperature, liquid temperature, fill level, and acceleration. Among these, the F-values clearly identify the liquid temperature as the most influential parameter. This is consistent with the assumption of complete thermal mixing, where the liquid—being at the lowest temperature in the the system—governs the reduction of saturation temperature following sloshing and thus predominantly determines the final tank pressure.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the Pv Fitted Model

Source	DF	Sum Squares	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value
Model	9	0.1481	0.0165	7.03	< 0.0001
g	1	7.47e-06	7.47e-06	0.0032	0.9554
h/D	1	0.0274	0.0274	11.69	0.0021
T_l	1	0.0671	0.0671	28.67	< 0.0001
$g - h/D$	1	0.0047	0.0047	1.99	0.1702
$g - T_l$	1	0.0144	0.0144	6.17	0.0197
$h/D - T_l$	1	0.0279	0.0279	11.93	0.0019
g^2	1	0.0167	0.0167	7.12	0.0130
T_l^2	1	0.0004	0.0004	0.1719	0.6818
T_l^3	1	0.0342	0.0342	14.62	0.0007
Residual	26	0.0608	0.0023		
Total	35	0.2090			

Table 4: Peq Model Summary

Statistic	Value
R-squared (R^2)	70.88%
Adjusted R-squared (R_{adj}^2)	60.81%
Predicted R-squared (R_{pred}^2)	48.78%

4. Conclusions

This work presents an experimental investigation of pressure drop phenomena in a non-isothermal storage tank subjected to vertical sloshing. A key focus was placed on characterizing the thermal response of the system during flow-induced mixing, with particular attention to the coupling between vapor condensation and tank depressurization. By computing the Nusselt number from a global energy balance, the study quantifies the intensity of vapor-phase heat transfer and links it directly to the observed pressure decay. The results show that cases with stronger sloshing and thermal mixing exhibit higher Nusselt numbers and larger pressure drops, confirming that condensation at the cooled interface is the dominant mechanism of heat transfer. A clear regime-based behavior was identified, with resonance-driven flow transitions playing a central role in triggering effective heat transfer and interface cooling.

A complementary Design of Experiments (DOE) analysis helped assess the influence of various parameters, revealing that the liquid temperature, closely tied to the degree of subcooling, is the most influential factor in determining the magnitude of the pressure drop. This highlights the significance of thermal stratification and the initial thermodynamic state in determining the system's response under dynamic conditions.

Future work will focus on a more detailed characterization of the Nusselt number as a function of the initial thermodynamic conditions, with particular emphasis on the degree of liquid subcooling. A deeper understanding of how subcooling influences interfacial heat transfer and condensation dynamics will support the development of more accurate predictive models for pressure evolution, contributing to the design and operation of liquid hydrogen tanks in aircraft applications.

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